

Navigating Post-Exile: Transformations and Transitions in the Latvian Exile Community after 1991

Version 1

Description

The project aims to explore the “post-exile” period of the Latvian exile community formed after World War II, highlighting its evolution following Latvia’s independence in 1991, when the “old exile” became part of the emerging diaspora. By examining the transformation of exile community identities, their relationships and ties to their homeland, the experiences of returnees, and the dynamics between the “old exile” and recent emigrants, the project will provide a nuanced understanding of the post-exile experience. A multidisciplinary approach, integrating historical and biographical research methods, will offer insights into individuals’ sense of belonging and identity development during a time marked by significant migration in Latvia and globally.

The research is conducted within the Fundamental and Applied Research Programme project "Navigating Post-Exile: Transformations and Transitions in the Latvian Exile Community after 1991" (project No. LZP-2024/1-0114), funded by the Latvian Council of Science.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Navigating Post-Exile:
Transformations and
Transitions in the Latvian Exile

Community after 1991 (No.
Izp-2024/1-0114)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Navigating Post-Exile: Transformations and Transitions in the Latvian Exile Community after 1991

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Navigating Post-Exile: Transformations and Transitions in the Latvian Exile Community after 1991 (No. Izp-2024/1-0114)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

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4. Templates

Descriptions

In-depth interviews

In-depth interviews with members of the (post)exile community and the new diaspora to gather contemporary perspectives on their experiences before, during, and after Latvia's independence.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the in-depth interviews is to provide a nuanced understanding of the lived realities of exiles and valuable context for interpreting historical events and trends. By capturing a broad spectrum of voices, these interviews will offer fresh perspectives on the transformations, identities, and contributions of Latvian exiles in the post-independence era, deepening the understanding of their evolving identity and role after 1991.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Textual data
- Other

Audio data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- MP3
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data collected through in-depth interviews will be valuable for researchers in migration studies, oral history, and diaspora studies, providing firsthand insights into the lived experiences of Latvian exiles and diaspora. It may also be useful for policymakers and cultural institutions interested in historical memory, identity formation, and the social integration of returnees. Additionally, the data could benefit educators and students in related fields, as well as the broader public interested in Latvia's exile history and post-independence transformations.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

A catalog will be created, listing all interviews with unique identification numbers and key information about the interviewees. Each interview will be assigned keywords, and in some cases, annotations and transcripts will be prepared to facilitate data accessibility and research use. The metadata will support the organization, discoverability, and contextualization of the interviews while ensuring compliance with ethical and data protection standards.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The data generated through in-depth interviews will have restricted access, available upon request, due to the inclusion of personal and sensitive information. The collected data will include names, birthdates, and audio recordings, as well as potentially sensitive details regarding ethnicity, political views, and religious or philosophical beliefs. All personal data will be obtained with the voluntary informed consent of participants, documented through signed consent forms. The interview recordings and related materials will be securely stored in the National Oral History (NOHA) collection at the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, Faculty of Humanities, University of Latvia. Data will be preserved following NOHA's

principles, ensuring controlled access and compliance with data protection regulations, including the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Latvian Personal Data Processing Law. Access to the data will be granted only to authorized individuals and researchers who submit a formal request and meet ethical and legal requirements.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

The in-depth interviews will be conducted by experienced researchers following established methodological guidelines to ensure the reliability and consistency of the data. Audio recordings will be of high quality to facilitate accurate transcription. Transcriptions, where needed, will be carefully reviewed and, if necessary, corrected to ensure fidelity to the original recordings. Additionally, data will be securely stored and systematically documented, including metadata describing the context, methodology, and any relevant modifications. All procedures will comply with ethical and legal standards, including GDPR, to maintain data integrity and confidentiality.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Maija Krūmiņa (0000-0002-5008-9221)

- Ginta Elksne (0000-0003-1011-3351)

Data description and processing will be ensured by researchers Ginta Elksne and Maija Krūmiņa.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

Data will be stored on information systems managed by the University of Latvia (data storage, access control).

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

There are ethical and legal considerations that could impact data collection and sharing. These include the need for informed consent from participants, ensuring that they fully understand how their personal data will be used, stored, and shared. Sensitive information such as ethnicity, political views, and religious beliefs may be collected, which requires careful handling to ensure confidentiality and compliance with data protection regulations (GDPR and national laws).

Additionally, the right to withdraw from the study at any time is guaranteed, and any data associated with withdrawn participants will be deleted. Furthermore, any pseudonymization of data for research purposes must be done in accordance with the participants' wishes and legal requirements, ensuring privacy is maintained throughout the study.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Privacy constraints
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- National laws
- Pseudonymization

Personal data and sensitive information will be processed in accordance with GDPR and national data protection laws. Data will be securely stored in the National Oral History (NOHA) collection at the University of Latvia, with access restricted to authorized researchers upon request. No anonymization will be applied, but pseudonymization may be used in publications if requested by participants. Participants can withdraw their data at any time, in which case all related materials will be permanently deleted.

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